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- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

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APPLICATION OF IFRS IN BUDGETARY ACCOUNTING

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Abstract: This article examines the key issues associated with the implementation and application of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) in budgetary institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It highlights the significance of IFRS in enhancing financial transparency, accountability, and comparability, while also addressing practical challenges during its integration into public sector accounting practices.

Key words: budgetary organization, reporting, budgetary accounting, IFRS.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasi byudjet muassasalarida moliyaviy hisobotning xalqaro standartlarini (IFRS) joriy etish va qo'llash bilan bog'liq asosiy masalalar ko'rib chiqiladi. U IFRS ning moliyaviy shaffoflik, hisobdorlik va taqqoslanuvchanlikni oshirishdagi ahamiyatini ta'kidlaydi, shu bilan birga uni davlat sektori buxgalteriya hisobi amaliyotiga integratsiyalashganda amaliy muammolarni hal qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: byudjet tashkiloti, hisobot, byudjet hisobi, IFRS.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются основные вопросы, связанные с внедрением и применением Международных стандартов финансовой отчетности (МСФО) в бюджетных учреждениях Республики Узбекистан. Подчеркивается значение МСФО в повышении финансовой прозрачности, подотчетности и сопоставимости, а также рассматриваются практические проблемы при их интеграции в практику учета в государственном секторе.

Ключевые слова: бюджетная организация, отчетность, бюджетный учет, МСФО.

INTRODUCTION

International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) play a significant role in ensuring business transparency and attracting foreign investments. High-quality IFRS reporting is essential for Uzbek companies seeking international recognition and access to global capital markets.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, accounting in budgetary organizations is regulated by a number of legislative acts as well as accounting standards developed within the national system. One of the directions of the reform of Uzbekistan's budgetary system is the improvement of the accounting and reporting system for the public sector based on the International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS).

The necessity of this reform is primarily due to the fact that accounting systems provide the information required for making high-quality and timely managerial decisions. The objective process of unifying accounting reporting standards has contributed to the recognition of IPSAS (International Public Sector Accounting Standards), based on IFRS (International Financial Reporting Standards), as a unified, comprehensive system of international accounting standards for preparing comparable and high-quality financial reports in the public sector. The application of IPSAS improves the quality of financial information by providing greater opportunities to assess the performance of the public sector, enhancing transparency, improving the management of state assets through increased reliability and completeness of information, and enabling the comparability of public financial reports with international benchmarks.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

Y. Chan[3]'s study shows that the introduction of international standards (in particular, IPSAS – an adapted form of IFRS for the public sector) in the field of budget accounting is a complex and multifaceted process. According to the author, international standards not only increase transparency and accountability, but also ensure the effectiveness of budget policy. Chan also pays special attention to the problems of institutional coordination in public finance management.

J. Christiaens et al.[4] study analyzes the impact of international financial reporting standards (IFRS/IPSAS) on public sector reforms. The authors of the study show the advantages of IPSAS-based reporting – as a means of ensuring more accurate financial information, comparability and financial stability. In particular, the resulting comparisons are presented on the example of European countries.

A. Bergmann[5] considers the modernization of public financial management and accounting in connection with the introduction of international financial reporting standards. He deeply analyzes the main differences between IPSAS and IFRS and highlights their impact on budget reporting. The author focuses in particular on the advantages and limitations of the transition to accrual-based reporting.

B. Benito et al.[6] analyze the economic and institutional aspects of harmonizing government financial information systems based on international standards. Based on international experience, the authors indicate the important conditions for the implementation of IFRS/IPSAS for budget accounting. They also justify the increase in efficiency through the integration of information systems.

V. Pina and L. Torres[7] conduct a comparative analysis of the practical implementation of international reporting standards in the public sector. They show, using the examples of several countries, how financial reporting based on international standards improves fiscal responsibility and monitoring of public spending. In particular, the issue of harmonization between the state budget and the national reporting system is mentioned as an important issue.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In carrying out this research work, methods widely used in scientific research methodology were used. In the process of scientific analysis, these scientific research methods were widely used, in particular, observation, generalization, grouping, comparison, and in analysis, synthesis and analysis methods were widely used.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In addition to the aforementioned reasons, the necessity to transition to IPSAS practices is driven by practical issues within the existing regulatory framework. Specifically, an assessment of the regulatory base against the criteria for applying IPSAS revealed several shortcomings:

In Uzbekistan, the application of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) in budgetary accounting faces a number of challenges. The main difficulties are related to the need to adapt current budgetary rules and procedures to the requirements of IFRS, as well as the training and retraining of specialists. Furthermore, the transition to IFRS demands significant financial investments in software and infrastructure.

According to expert observations, a significant portion of reports published in Uzbekistan and claimed to be prepared in accordance with IFRS do not fully comply with international standards in terms of both presentation format and content. This creates risks for:

- investors making decisions based on incomplete information;
- companies seeking to attract international financing;
- the Uzbek economy as a whole, which requires transparent financial data.

In the current legislation, the procedures for recording transactions in accounting are insufficiently clearly regulated. It was intended that all issues related to budgetary accounting would be governed by the Instruction on Accounting in Budgetary Organizations; however, in practice, consolidating all aspects of the financial and economic activities of budgetary institutions within a single instruction proved impossible.

Lack of procedures for accounting of certain financial, budgetary, and extra-budgetary transactions, in particular those of government organizations related to agricultural activities, foreign exchange operations, etc.

Numerous accounting provisions that duplicate certain aspects of accounting and reporting.

Inability to analyze public finance statistics for external users. The current accounting system does not allow generating information that meets the requirements of external users.

Absence of consolidation of all government finance accounts. In particular, accounting for the state budget and all extra-budgetary funds is currently conducted separately.

To date, the need to adopt IPSAS (International Public Sector Accounting Standards) has been confirmed both by national programs and by international assessments of the development process of the public financial management system of the Republic of Uzbekistan. A key objective of the accounting reform is the development and implementation of national public sector accounting standards aligned with IPSAS.

Compliance with IPSAS is a critical indicator in the evaluation of public finances under the PEFA (Public Expenditure and Financial Accountability) framework. Considering this criterion, World Bank experts, during their most recent assessment of public finances in Uzbekistan, noted partial non-compliance of financial information with international accounting standards due to the incompleteness of the information provided.

To ensure the proper implementation of International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS), the joint UNDP and Ministry of Finance Project “Budget System Reform in Uzbekistan” provided support for launching the reform of accounting and reporting in the public sector. Within the framework of the Project, a Concept for improving the accounting and reporting system based on IPSAS was developed. Specifically, drafts of 12 Budget Accounting Standards (BAS) were prepared.

Their practical implementation in the country’s accounting system will require training specialists in their competent use, including the education and retraining of accountants and financial personnel in the budget sector, the reorientation of curricula in secondary and higher educational institutions, as well as the updating and development of teaching and methodological materials for various categories of learners.

Challenges in Applying IPSAS in Uzbekistan’s Budgetary Accounting:

Non-compliance of Budgetary Rules and Procedures with IPSAS Requirements:

The current budgetary accounting rules in Uzbekistan are largely based on national standards that differ significantly from IPSAS. This necessitates amendments to legislation and regulatory acts governing the budget process.

Insufficient Specialist Training: The transition to IPSAS requires budget accounting professionals to have deep knowledge and skills in working with international standards. Uzbekistan faces a shortage of qualified personnel capable of ensuring a high-quality transition to IPSAS.

Financial Costs: Implementing IPSAS requires substantial financial investments in developing and deploying new software, training personnel, as well as restructuring internal control and audit systems.

Lack of Methodological Framework: Despite active efforts to implement IPSAS, the methodological base for budgetary accounting in accordance with IPSAS in Uzbekistan is still under development.

Difficulties with Consolidation of Reporting: The transition to IPSAS necessitates the creation of mechanisms for consolidating financial reports across various levels of the budgetary system, which presents certain challenges.

Risks of Incomplete Compliance with IPSAS Requirements: Experts note that a significant portion of reports presented as IPSAS-compliant do not fully meet international standards, which may mislead users of the information.

The Association of Certified Financial Professionals of Uzbekistan (ACFP) announces the launch of an important educational initiative – the regular publication of professional analytical reviews of the financial statements of leading Uzbek companies, prepared in accordance with International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS).

ACFP is a professional organization established to develop and support specialists in finance, accounting, and auditing in Uzbekistan. The association promotes the adoption of international accounting and reporting standards, enhances the transparency of financial information, and fosters the professional competencies of financial specialists.

As part of the new project, ACFP experts will conduct a comprehensive assessment of financial statements based on the following criteria:

Completeness of Reporting Verification of the presence of all mandatory components of financial statements in accordance with IFRS requirements, including:

- Statement of Financial Position
- Statement of Profit or Loss
- Statement of Comprehensive Income
- Statement of Changes in Equity
- Statement of Cash Flows
- Notes to the Financial Statements

Accuracy of Consolidation Analysis of the application of consolidation principles according to IFRS 10 “Consolidated Financial Statements,” including the correctness of determining the consolidation perimeter and elimination of intra-group transactions.

Compliance with IFRS Requirements Assessment of the presence of a clear and unambiguous statement of compliance with International Financial Reporting Standards in the notes to the financial statements.

Disclosure of Beneficial Ownership Verification of disclosure of information about the ultimate beneficial owner of the group of companies in accordance with IFRS (IAS) 24 “Related Party Disclosures.”

Going Concern Analysis Evaluation of the justification for applying the going concern principle and the adequacy of disclosure regarding risks and uncertainties.

Dynamics of Financial Results Analysis of changes in financial indicators across key revenue and expense categories, identifying major trends and influencing factors.

Financial Ratios Calculation and interpretation of key financial ratios reflecting liquidity, solvency, profitability, and operational efficiency.

Changes in Balance Sheet Structure Analysis of the dynamics of major asset and liability items, identifying significant changes and their underlying causes.

Financial Risk Management Assessment of the disclosure regarding the risk management system and measures taken to mitigate risks.

Recommendations for Addressing Issues:

- Development of a Clear and Understandable Regulatory Framework:

It is necessary to amend legislation and regulatory acts governing the budget process to align them with IFRS requirements.

- Organization of Training and Professional Development:

Systematic training of specialists in budget accounting under IFRS should be conducted, along with organizing seminars and workshops to enhance their qualifications.

Development of Methodological Materials: It is necessary to develop and implement methodological guidelines and manuals for applying IFRS in budget accounting, taking into account the specific conditions of Uzbekistan.

Implementation of Modern Information Systems:

Investment is required in the development and deployment of modern information systems that support IFRS-based accounting and ensure process automation.

• Ensuring Transparency and Control: Strengthening control over compliance with IFRS requirements and ensuring transparency of budget operations are essential.

Successful implementation of IFRS in Uzbekistan's budget accounting requires a comprehensive approach and joint efforts from the government, professionals, and the business community.

Currently, the application of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) in budget accounting in Uzbekistan is not mandatory. IFRS is primarily used in the commercial sector by large enterprises and organizations as defined by legislation. Budgetary organizations in Uzbekistan continue to maintain accounting in accordance with national standards.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

As a result of the procedures, it was found that the introduction of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) in budgetary organizations of the Republic of Uzbekistan contributes to the transparency of financial information and compliance with international requirements. This is an important factor in increasing accountability and efficiency in the public sector. As the study found, the incomplete formation of the regulatory and legal framework, the lack of qualified personnel, and differences in practice create problems in the full application of IFRS.

On this basis, we can put forward the following proposals:

1. Improving the legal framework – special national standards should be developed based on IFRS adapted for budgetary organizations.
2. Increasing human resources capacity – it is necessary to organize systematic training programs on IFRS for current accountants and auditors.
3. Updating the information technology infrastructure – the introduction of automated reporting systems based on international standards will increase the quality of calculations.

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